

Effect of Applying the E-Learning Learning Model as a Solution to the Covid-19 Pandemic on Student Learning Outcomes

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ABSTRACT

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The process of development of science and technology in this era is growing rapidly. This is in line with the times, we are faced with a world problem, namely the COVID-19 pandemic which requires us to comply with health protocols and avoid crowds to reduce the process of spreading the covid-19 virus. The effect of implementing these regulations resulted in the teaching and learning process that should have been carried out face to face to become network-based learning. The use of E-learning media is expected to overcome learning limitations due to the covid-19 pandemic. So, when conducting research it was found that learning with E-learning media had not been able to provide satisfactory results on student learning outcomes, where student learning outcomes did not reach the target KKM value = 75. Many factors influenced this including not all students who have smartphones and low network signal quality.

INTRODUCTION

Our country is a country that ever growing need reliable human resources to be able to compete with other countries. This reliable human resource can be seen from the improvement in the quality of education. Education is one of the important things in improving human resources. The quality of human resources depends on the quality of education. The role of education is to create an intelligent, peaceful, open and democratic society. The quality of human resources in Indonesia is still low. Physics is one of the basic sciences that plays an important role in studying this subject. Physics is a science learn about materials or substances that includes physical properties, composition, changes, and energy produced (Abidin, 2020) Physics also plays an important role in mastering science and technology which is increasingly sophisticated and modern. The low interest of students is deemed necessary to evacuate the teaching and learning process by looking at the level of success of students in student self-confidence, reflecting on and improving learning models and strategies (Hasibuan, 2021).

Student learning outcomes are influenced by two factors, namely internal factors and student external factors. Internal student factors include health problems, disabilities, psychological factors (intelligence, interest in learning, attention, talent, motivation, maturity and readiness of students), and fatigue factors. While the external factors that influence student learning processes and outcomes include family, school and community factors. Student learning interest has many positive effects on learning processes and outcomes, high interest will lead to a level of attention and readiness level of students involved in learning objects so as to raise the possibility of success in learning (Nurhasanah, 2016).

The world of education is currently being hit by massive duping due to the absence of face-to-face learning activities due to the covid-19 pandemic until now. Education currently carried out online has not been fully able to overcome learning problems. The Indonesian government implements a Work from Home (WFH) policy for workers. This policy is applied to the community so that they can complete their work at home. Education in Indonesia is also one of the areas affected by the covid-19 pandemic. There are restrictions on interaction The Ministry of Education in Indonesian also issued a policy, namely by closing schools starting from PAUD to student lectures and replacing the government's Teaching and Learning Activities (KBM) process by implementing online learning policies (online/E-learning). By using this E-learning learning system, various problems faced by students and teachers sometimes arise, such as learning material that has not been delivered by the teacher and then the teacher replaces the task with another task (Marharjono, 2020).

The transfer of teaching and learning activities using technology in the form of smartphones or laptops requires educators to be able to adapt to the current situation (Zahraini, 2021). E-Learning learning is a form of utilizing internet technology for learning experiences. E-Learning can also be seen as a form of innovation in the learning process that can be designed properly, which

is more user-centered, more interactive which has various conveniences for users because it can be accessed anytime and anywhere. E-Learning is a way of utilizing digital technology for the learning process so that learning can be more open, distributed and flexible. (Aurora, 2019). The e-learning system is a form of implementing learning using the internet through websites and weblogs with multimedia content which is a process of transformation and digitization of conventional learning. E-learning allows individuals to plan and direct their own learning process, so that each student takes responsibility or learns according to their own awareness (Arifin, 2018). E-learning systems vary from simple ones, namely just a collection of learning materials placed on a web server with additional communication forums via e-mail separately, to integrated ones, such as e-learning portals which contain various learning objects enriched with multimedia and combined with academic information system, evaluation, communication, discussion and various other educational tools (Susilo, 2020).

One of the reasons that support why students have to study independently is that nowadays there are many learning resources that students can get from various media. Learning is not limited to school only, but can be anywhere and anytime. Now the teacher is no longer the only source of learning for students. It is students who must actively learn independently to build their own knowledge. The application of technology in the learning process in schools has slowly begun to be implemented in Indonesia.

LITERATURE RIVIEW

In line with the continued development of technology and the expansion of these technological advances to the interior, even with the limitations, learning can now be done via a computer that has access to the internet. During the Covid-19 pandemic, E-learning was one of the ways in which the learning process was carried out. But in reality in the field, E-learning cannot be fully implemented or can replace the normal face-to-face learning process. So that on this occasion, researchers conducted a study of the effect of E-learning during the Covid-19 pandemic on the physics learning outcomes of class XI students at SMK Negeri 1 Tantom Tapanuli Selatan.

METHODS

One thing that is no less important in carrying out research activities is to determine a research method that is appropriate and suitable for the problem under study. The selection of appropriate research methods greatly influences the results of the research to be achieved. Sugiyono said "The research method is a scientific way to obtain data with specific purposes and uses" (Sugiyono, 2008). Explain your methodologies in this chapter. You should explain your research instruments, data collection processes, data analysis processes or hypothesis testing processes, and data display processes.

So that the research method used is experimental research which is a method used to see whether there is a change that occurs after giving a treatment to research subjects who are a source of data for researchers. Data

collection techniques were carried out by distributing pre-tests, post-tests and questionnaires/questions. Questionnaires are used to determine student responses to the implementation of E-Learning, while tests are used to measure student learning outcomes as quantitative data to be analyzed.

RESULTS

Initial class test data were obtained through a pre-test and post-test data were obtained through a post-test which was filled in by 36 students. The pre-test and post-test use 20 multiple choice questions with a score of 0 - 100, so the theoretical score for the minimum score is 0 with $0 \times 5 = 0$ and the maximum score is 100 with $20 \times 5 = 100$. From the results of the pretest it was found that student learning outcomes were still below the KKM score = 75 while for the post-test results it was also found that student learning outcomes were still below KKM = 75. The difference in physics learning outcomes is quite significant between before learning (pre-test) and after learning (post-test).

Figure 1. Pre-Test Frequency of Class X TKJ 1 SMK Negeri 1 Tantom Angkola

Figure 2. Post-test Frequency of Class X TKJ 1 SMK Negeri 1 Tantom Angkola

Figure 3. Comparison between Pre-Test Frequency and Post-Test Frequency of Class X TKJ 1 SMK Negeri 1 Tantom Angkola

In Figure 1, Figure 2 and Figure 3 you can see the difference. It was found that the average student pretest score was 47.56 while the average student post-test score was 56.89. This is caused by the many student complaints in the online learning process or with E-learning learning. Obstacles faced by students include not all students having smartphones, package quotas, signals and students not being active in the online learning process. Then by using a questionnaire, the results obtained from the distribution of the frequency of the questionnaire show that the score for choosing doubtful is in the interval 40 - 59.9 with a percentage value of 63.89%. And the score that appears the most is at a score of 56 with 8 students and can be seen in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Questionnaire percentage of Class X TKJ 1 SMK Negeri 1 Tantom Angkola

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the research results, learning using E-elearning learning media in physics learning is significantly less good than without using e-learning because student activity is lower. Especially during the time of the corona virus (Covid-19), the Indonesian government announced that all schools should study online instead of face-to-face as usual. At the beginning of learning, the conditioning of students in the WhatsApp group experienced a few obstacles. Students are still confused because learning media with e-learning is still a new thing for them. Not all students have smartphones and low signal quality in the regions is one of the obstacles that results in not optimal learning with E-learning learning media.

RECOMMENDATIONS

During the Covid-19 pandemic, it was the application of online learning that was actually not able to overcome student learning. this is caused by the limitations of both students in terms of mastery in using e-learning, not all students have smartphones, poor network and data packages.

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